

The Effect of Functionalized Cellulose Nanocrystals on Glass Fiber-Epoxy Composite Performance

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Presentation Outline

1. Background:

- Glass fiber (GF) polymer composites & Cellulose Nanocrystals (CNC)

2. Objectives

3. Methods

- Coating CNC onto GF fabrics
- GF-CNC-Epoxy Laminates

4. Results

- Interfacial properties
- Mechanical performance

5. Conclusions

Glass Fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites for Automotive Applications

- Low cost & high-volume production
- Versatile
- Lightweight
 - **Better fuel efficiency**
 - **Lower carbon footprint**

Fuel economy & CO₂ emissions trends for car manufacturers ¹

1) United States Environmental Protection Agency (EPA)

Glass Fiber Polymer Composite & Nanocellulose

- **Cellulose nanocrystals (CNC)**

- High abundance & renewable
- Improves mechanical properties of GF composites when dispersed in resin²
- Improves **interfacial shear strength** of GF composites when dispersed in sizing^{3,4}

Matrix with CNC

Matrix

Interphase

2) Haque, E., et al. *Cellulose* 28, 4685–4700 (2021)

3) Asadi, A., et al. *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 88, 206–215. (2016)

4) Goswami, J., et al. *Materials*, 12(12), 1951. (2019)

CNC Hydrophilicity and Aggregation as a Major Challenge

Coating aqueous CNC onto GF

- Circumvents difficulties with dispersing CNC in resins
- Targets the GF-matrix interface directly.

Objective 1: Develop the methodology for slot die coating with vacuum assist to deposit CNC onto glass fiber fabric.

Chemical modification of CNC

- Facilitate CNC chemical bonding at GF-matrix interface.
- Hydrophobic functionalization reduces water absorption from CNC particles

Objective 2: Study the effect of functionalized CNC coatings on GFRC interface and performance.

Pathway for high-volume application of CNC and producing stronger GFRP composites using renewable resources.

Slot Die Coating CNC onto GF Fabric

Slot Die Coating Materials:

- Substrate:
 - E-glass fabric, unidirectional
- Coating fluid:
 - Commercial aqueous CNC from CelluForce (H₂SO₄ hydrolysis process) 1wt% dispersed in DI water
 - Cellulose modified with tannic acid & hexadecylamine^{5,6}
1 wt% dispersion in ethanol

Composite Manufacture Materials:

- E-glass fabric, unidirectional
- Epoxy resin: DGEBA Thin Epoxy + Hardener system

Slot Die Coating CNC onto GF Fabric

The Effect of Vacuum on Coating Morphology

The Effect of Vacuum on Coating Morphology

No vacuum

Caked film on top of fabric

With vacuum

Good fiber separation on top of fabric

GFRC Manufacture & Characterization

Characterization techniques

- Single fiber fragmentation test
- Void content (ASTM D2734-94)
- Flexural (3-point-bend ASTM 7264)
- Interlaminar shear strength (ASTM D2344)

Schematic of hand-lay up and vacuum bagging only (VBO) process for epoxy GFRCs.

Characterization of CNC and CNC-coated GF Fabric

- Contact angle of DI water on CNC films increases following modification with tannic acid and hexadecylamine.

- Presence of CNC confirmed using O-H stretching from cellulose pyranose rings at 3320 cm^{-1}
- Hexadecylamine produces C10-alkyl peak at 2920 cm^{-1}

Sample names for GF fabric

As-received	AR
Unmodified CNC	CNC_UM
Modified CNC	CNC_M

FTIR Spectra of GF Fabric

Coated GF Fabric under SEM

- More surface roughness helps mechanical interlocking between CNC and epoxy at the interphase

The Effect of CNC on GF-Epoxy Interfacial Adhesion

- **The Single Fiber Fragmentation Test (SFFT)**
 - External stress applied to coupon is transferred to the fiber through the matrix-fiber interface/interphase.
 - More efficient stress transfer through the interphase → higher fragment count.
- **Photo-elastic Effects & Birefringence Patterns**
 - If the interface is weak, the fractured fiber will de-bond (3) and slip within the matrix, reducing the fragment count.
 - If the interface is strong, the fiber crack will also propagate into the matrix, causing disk (1) or cone shaped (2) cracks/deformations.

Single fiber in epoxy coupon fractures with slowly applied tensile load.

The Effect of CNC on GF-Epoxy Interfacial Adhesion

- All formulations are compatible with GF and epoxy

The Effect of CNC on Laminate Properties

Flexural Properties

- CNC_M and CNC_UM produce improved flexural properties of laminates
- CNC_M largest improvement of 36% in modulus and 30% in strength

Fracture surface morphology

- Increased matrix residue on fibers with CNC coating → greater adhesion and interfacial interaction
- CNC bonds with silane

The Effect of CNC on Laminate Properties

Interlaminar Shear Strength

- As-received and CNC_UM performed the same
- CNC_M demonstrates 19% improvement over As-received

Summary

- CNC coating on GF can enhance the interfacial adhesion between GF-epoxy
- Chemically functionalized CNC can provide greater improvement to interfacial, flexural, and interlaminar properties
 - Synergistic effect between mechanical interlocking & chemical bonding
 - Improved compatibility and resin wetting
- Future of CNC as a sizing material compatible with commercial formulations?

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